

WAYS TO DEVELOP THE ORGANIZATION OF MARKETING RESEARCH IN
AGRICULTURE

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***Abstract.** In this article, the collection of information about the markets of agricultural products, the determination of changes in supply and demand, the selection of the market segment and the organization of the necessary funds and material capabilities, control and the implementation of the results of the producers of agricultural products are considered.*

***Keywords:** Marketing research, agriculture, product, farmer, infrastructure, consumer, cluster.*

INTRODUCTION. Nowadays, farms, councils and even private farms have to operate in a competitive market environment. They themselves do not have the ability to independently study the market and conduct special marketing research. For this reason, the organization of seminars and consultations for them with the participation of specialists of special educational and scientific institutions is considered one of the urgent issues of this day.

The development of the market infrastructure, together with the improvement of the processes of delivery and sale of agricultural products to the consumer, encourages them to produce, store and process more and better quality products. In order to adapt to the market conditions that arise as a result of such a process, it is important to establish a marketing service in enterprises that grow and process agricultural products, in particular, in farms and their councils.

Modernization requires, first of all, to renew the network technically and technologically, and morally based on the re-equipment of production with the most advanced modern technologies. The effective implementation of all activities in this area, defined in the main directions of agricultural modernization, creates an opportunity to raise the economic efficiency of production to an optimal level based on a sharp increase in the competitiveness of primary agricultural products grown in agriculture, including farms, which are considered the main form of economic management. These things can only be done by relying on the Marketing of Today.

Conducting marketing research in all sectors of the economy acquires its own complexity. Today, in the agriculture of our republic, farmers and peasant farms and partially agro-firms operate. It is known that farms grow products mainly according to the state order and partly for their own needs (police and horticulture). This, in turn, causes problems related to the production, sale and transportation of products at the lowest cost. The purpose of these studies is to determine the strategy tactics of agricultural enterprises in the market and ensure that they achieve more success and advantage over competitors.

In marketing research, cluster analysis methods are used effectively and are among the most common methods. The cluster method is also known as the grouping method in statistics. Cluster analysis by Uzbek scientists is mainly recognized as "statistical grouping" in scientific literature. Many scientific studies have been carried out by scientists of the world and our country on the use of cluster analysis methods in the segmentation of the food products market. The use of cluster analysis in marketing research and its methodological aspects are widely

studied in the scientific literature of N. Malhotra, M. Porter and A. Aayker. In particular, N. Malhotra and A. Aayker explained the use of cluster analysis in marketing research using segmentation methods that are mainly implemented in the consumer sector. M. Porter's theories used cluster analysis methods to distinguish specific aspects of countries' competitive advantages and conducted research on the formation of network clusters. V. Smid and Y. Vindlar conducted the first scientific studies on the use of the cluster analysis method in market segmentation. These studies have been the main impetus for expanding the scope of meta-research of marketing conducted on market segmentation.

It was emphasized the need to introduce a modern management system in the food and alcohol industry in our country, to sharply increase the volume of production, to increase the assortment and improve the quality of exportable products with extensive use of marketing and innovation, and to establish a new system aimed at finding new markets. The specified task determines the need to select the most target markets for Uzbekistan and develop marketing strategies aimed at penetrating these markets.

In order to carry out the cluster analysis, it is first necessary to form information on determining the main competitors for the Republic of Uzbekistan and their position in the market in the world market of juice products. The main source of data is the information of the "Market Access MapITC" database (www.trademap.org), which is the official portal of the International Trade Organization. Developed by ITC to support the needs of exporters, trade promotion institutions, trade policy makers and academic institutions in developing countries. It provides information on customs definitions (including tariff exemptions) applied by more than 200 countries and with 239 countries and territories. In addition, taking this into account, the main goal of marketing services in agriculture can be said to be effective use of all opportunities based on the market conditions that may arise at a certain time, based on demand, supply, price, quality level and other conjunctural indicators.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. In order to achieve this goal, the following main tasks are to be fulfilled:

- collection of information on the markets of agricultural products to determine changes in supply and demand;
- selection of a market segment suitable for targeted activity, allowing producers of agricultural products to use them effectively based on their capabilities;
- organization of funds and material resources necessary for the implementation of activities, implementation of control and assessment of results.

Nowadays, farms, councils and even private farms have to operate in a competitive market environment. They themselves do not have the ability to independently study the market and conduct special marketing research. For this reason, the organization of seminars and consultations for them with the participation of specialists of special educational and scientific institutions is considered one of the urgent issues of this day. Improving the marketing culture of enterprises and organizations that grow and process agricultural products is one of the activities aimed at increasing the efficiency of their activities. We believe that it is appropriate to consider the following suggestions when organizing a marketing service for the cultivation of agricultural products:

- organization of adaptation of producers' capabilities to market demands and needs;
- organization of raising the economic knowledge of producers of agricultural products, that is, farmers and agricultural specialists;
- selection of a responsible employee to conduct marketing service in the cultivation of agricultural products;

At the modern stage of economic development, competitiveness is the only criterion for improving and ensuring the quality of agricultural products and services.

Product to increase competitiveness

(goods and services), is characteristic of the enterprise, the region and the country as a whole, and occupies an important place as the main link of the economy.

Working in the field of agriculture in the market economy agricultural enterprises to success reach economy careful planning of effective development of activities and own opportunities and prospects about depends on being armed with the necessary information.

Among the important conditions for the emergence of competition in the conditions of the modern market economy, the following can be included:

complete economic (economic) independence of each goods-producing and service-providing firms;

the complete dependence of the producer's activity on the market situation;

to face all other commodity producers in the competition for demand.

Currently, there are different directions of research of the concept of "competitiveness". The famous Austrian economist, the founder of the evolutionary theory of economic development, Y. Schumpeter defined competition as a struggle between innovation and the old.

The main purpose of cluster analysis in marketing research is to identify a group of countries with large export potential. Grouping countries on the basis of objectively defined criteria is based on the assumption of some degree of homogeneity for exporting enterprises. Based on this hypothesis, clustering is segmented into 5 main areas of fruit and vegetable importing countries. "Ward's" method of hierarchical clustering is used, assuming that the measurement units are of different forms according to the selected criteria. This method groups countries based on the dispersion of values for selected criteria. Using "Ward's" method, countries are divided into 5 main segments.

Enterprise competitiveness is the ability to conduct effective economic activity and profit in competitive market conditions.

Enterprise competitiveness is a set of characteristics that reflect the superiority of an economic entity over a rival enterprise in terms of indicators such as financial, economic, marketing, production, technological, personnel potential and ecology during a certain period of time under specific market conditions. It is the ability of the economic entity to operate without crisis and quickly adapt to the changing external environment. An English economist, a famous representative of the classical school, A. Smith explained competition as a category of behavior. Individual sellers and buyers compete in the market for advantageous sales and purchases, respectively. Competition is considered the "invisible hand" of the market and regulates the activities of its participants. The purpose of competition is to gain more profit.

A. Smith's contribution to the development of the theory of competition can be reflected in the priority directions of the development of farms: achievements, experiences and

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prospective plans. He was one of the first to define competition as a struggle. The main principle of competition is the principle of "invisible hands". He theoretically developed a mechanism of competition that equalizes the rate of profit in the network, leading to an efficient allocation of resources between networks. Given the existence of a large number of sellers and buyers, he determined the main conditions for effective competition, which does not allow each seller to significantly affect the change in the market price of a commodity.

Enterprise competitiveness includes the price and quality of agricultural products, as well as regulation of the flow of financial resources, management level. The level of competitiveness is affected by various situations that occur in one or another market, such as the introduction of innovations, financial stability, motivation of personnel with advanced methods and methods, and categorization.

Effective marketing activities play an important role in increasing the competitiveness of an agro-firm. Because it is marketing that is aimed at realizing the most necessary requirements of buyers, taking into account changes in consumer tastes, building effective and practical methods of increasing competitiveness.

Table 7

Product competitiveness indicators

No	Naming	Explanation	An example
1.	Normative	How much the product meets the standards and requirements established by law level of response	Compliance with minimum requirements, DAST, etc
2.	Technician	Buy removable and to meet a specific need directly directional of the goods feature and description	Available on certain parameters to the descriptions suitable coming in use amenities, service life, service of showing duration etc
3.	Economical	What the consumer does in the process of buying the product and using it in the future expenses value in money	Selling price based on product description The cost of material and spare parts necessary to maintain its condition in use

One of the important conditions of competitiveness is the quality of the offered product, which has the ability to satisfy the needs of the population for agricultural products to one degree or another. Quality management of agricultural products plays an important role in ensuring the competitiveness of an agrofirma. Modeling of the competitive indicators of the product is carried out at the stage of its design. The presence of the ability to fully satisfy the requirements of buyers compared to the goods of competitors in the market reflects the competitiveness of the product. The ratio between product quality, service level and prices is the basis of ensuring the competitiveness of agricultural products in the market. In addition, various factors: advertising, brand reputation, etc. can have a direct impact.

The non-availability of the possibility to provide the necessary technical services to the goods sold by the agro-firm leads to the loss of competitive advantage. Therefore, in order to ensure product competitiveness, it is necessary to provide service to goods even after they are sold. If such supply is denied, then the consumer will seek help from rivals and cause it to defect to the full rival side. Therefore, in order to increase competitiveness, the enterprise should clearly and clearly plan the service system, taking into account all the possibilities of technical support.

It is appropriate to use cluster analysis methods in the analysis of the competitive environment, segmentation, pricing, and development of product strategies in the marketing practice of enterprises. The use of the cluster analysis method in the effective acquisition and segmentation of global markets increases the effectiveness of the marketing research.

Conclusion The international market of agricultural products is a very complex and diverse socio-economic system. The relations in it are greatly influenced by the abundance and uniqueness of the products, as well as the existence of interests of all countries. Entering the market of food products and taking its place is one of the diseases of the development of the national economy.

In order to enter this market in today's conditions, on the one hand, it requires the development of innovative technologies in agriculture, and on the other hand, the introduction of modern methods of marketing.

As a result of the conducted theoretical and practical research, the policy of increasing the competitiveness of agricultural products in the international market was analyzed and the following conclusions were reached regarding its improvement:

1. Agriculture is very important in increasing the international competitiveness of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is based on our geographic location, climate, and especially the hard work and scientific potential of our people. In this regard, the President has adopted a number of Decrees and Decisions aimed at rapid development of agriculture. Among these Decree No. PF-5853 "On approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", adopted on October 23, 2019, is particularly important. Along with the technological development of agriculture, increasing its export potential has an important place in the tasks set in the decree.

2. There is an increasing demand for a unique marketing complex - agromarketing - in the cultivation and sale of agricultural products. Agromarketing is considered one of the new promising directions in the marketing theory, and it focuses on the wider satisfaction of consumer needs and the development of economic relations in the field of agricultural products. The peculiarities of agromarketing include the variety of products, cultivation technologies, consumption goals, and the uniqueness of transportation and sale. In this regard, specific tools and methods are used in market research, product creation, presentation and marketing management.

3. Agricultural products occupy a large place in the composition of the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In January-December 2020, the total volume of products (services) of agriculture, forestry and fisheries is 260.3 trillion. 251.8 trillion soums, including farming and animal husbandry, hunting and services provided in these areas. soums, forestry - 6.7 trillion. soums, fisheries - 1.8 trillion. organized soum. The share of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in GDP was 28.2%.

4. At the same time, agricultural products have not found their place in the export of our country. With the decrease in the export of cotton fiber, other products have not been able to compensate for it. The fact that the export of agricultural products in 2020 decreased by 7% compared to 2019 can be considered as a negative situation. The main reason for this is that the producers of our republic do not have sufficient knowledge of marketing methods in the international market and export is not supported from a methodological point of view.

Adaptation of agromarketing to the sharia of our country and creation of unique methods are of great importance in the developed proposals for the development of export of agricultural products. In our dissertation, we developed the following proposals aimed at improving marketing activities in the field of export of agricultural products of Uzbekistan:

Improving the methodology of comprehensive research and evaluation of the foreign market. Applying the cluster method of marketing research in the foreign market of agricultural products allows us to get information not only on the capacity and composition of the market, but also on how appropriate it is for our exporters, how to penetrate and occupy it;

Organization of a centralized marketing service to a certain extent, that is, the formation of an intermediary that moves products in a certain part of the foreign market for certain types of products. Such a service allows to reduce costs of mediation in providing assistance to farmers and peasant farms;

To increase the market competitiveness of agricultural products, that is, to adjust their properties to market demand, to organize packing, certification, transportation and preparation for sale at a high level;

Improving the strategy of export of agricultural products. Such a strategy includes a multi-year program of acquiring a specific market and is widely used by large companies. We suggest adapting and developing this foreign experience to the conditions of Uzbekistan;

Application of modern sales technologies in the export of fruit and vegetable products with high export potential in agriculture. For example, in the use of agrofranchising technology, it is possible to increase export opportunities by using the brand of Uzbekistan's products in local firms or large sales companies in the market.

We believe that the application of the above proposals will expand the export potential of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan.

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